

Recommended citation: Bris, S. G. L., Rouvrais, S., Friã■Geirsson, T. V., & Villalonga, L. T. (2017). Decision Making Skills in Engineering Education. In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 508-516). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698153.

Decision Making Skills in Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

There is a growing concern about responsibility of decision makers. Professional and personal life environments are more than ever Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, and Ambiguous. This system paper discusses decision making skills in engineering education along three complementary perspectives: Maths-based, Social-based, and Career-based. This review sketches the premise of a transversal decision skills learning outcomes framework for the continuous enhancement of engineering education programmes around decision making skills, and in line with the evolution of graduate engineering profiles.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills

Keywords: Transversal skills, decision making, engineering and STEM education, learning outcomes.

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the organizational reliability depends on the ability of the actors to organize and reorganize in order to anticipate and cope with unexpected situations, including skills of improvisation, creative bricolage, and attitude of wisdom [1]. The context of this system paper is the growing concern about responsibility of decision makers. The world is more complex, with multiplex of forces and no cause-and-effect chain. Whether they are to act as experts in STEM or other fields, future engineers should be specifically prepared to making decisions in VUCA environments (i.e. Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, and Ambiguous).

How to prepare future engineers to make more reliable decisions in VUCA environments and equip them with decision making skills in formal curricula? This paper first recalls accreditation requirements around decision making in engineering. Along three perspectives of decision-making (DM), it proposes specific learning outcomes applicable for educational programme design or realignments, and presents for each some active or experiential courses to meet relevant skills. The three perspectives considered are (i) Maths-based DM, (ii) Social-based DM, and (iii) Career-based DM. Unified for the three perspectives, the paper then discusses the opportunities of a transversal decision skills learning outcomes framework.

1 PROGRAMME OUTCOMES AND TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

1.1 Accreditation requirements

Decision is not only about knowledge, it is also about skills. Skills relate to the “ability to apply *knowledge* to complete tasks and solve problems. Skills can be described as cognitive (use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) and practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments)” [2]. The ENAEE, which sets Programme Outcomes for Engineering Education accreditation in EU [3], introduced in 2015 priority in Decision Making and Judgment abilities. From now on, in Europe, the learning process should enable Master Degree graduates to demonstrate:

- ability to manage complex technical or professional activities or projects that can require *new strategic approaches*, taking responsibility for DM;
- ability to *integrate* knowledge and handle complexity, to *formulate* judgements with incomplete or limited information, that include reflecting on social and ethical responsibilities *linked* to the application of their knowledge and judgement.

In the CDIO Syllabus [4], decision analysis with uncertainty (ref. 2.1.4) and initiative and willingness to make decisions in the face of uncertainty (ref. 2.4.1) are requirements for personal and professional skills. Making complex technical decisions with uncertain and incomplete information is also a requirement for exercising judgment and critical reasoning (ref. 4.7.7). The European Qualification Framework, recalls at level 5 “competence to exercise management and supervision in contexts of work or study activities where there is unpredictable change”; and at level 6 “to manage complex technical or professional activities or projects, taking responsibility for DM in unpredictable work or study contexts”.

1.2 Multidimensional and transversal Decision Making skills for Education & Training

Judgment skills correlates to DM skills. Psychological explanations describe inaccuracy in forecasting. The central theme is that most people use mental

strategies called heuristics to cope with the complexities of making estimates. These heuristics can also lead to systemically biased judgments (e.g. over-optimism). Heuristics could thus lead to erroneous decisions. A new heuristic requires a learning time, if the environment is too volatile, actors will not have resources to mobilize adequate heuristics, leading possibly to dramatic consequences. Complexity can lead to information overload with effects on the DM process. Moreover, uncertainty and ambiguity have consequences on the level of performance. The conditions of VUCA environments strongly affect constraints the decision capacity. One has to understand VUCA characteristics and sources, and their effects on DM processes.

The concept of decision has multiple dimensions. For engineers, DM echoes in scientific methods (e.g. Math-based), human environment (e.g. Social-based), or even in professional pathways (e.g. Career-based). DM skills, been learned in one context or to master a special situation, are also transversal (i.e. “skills acquired in one context that, with adaptation, may be applied in another context” [2]). Students are to capture the multiplicity of contextual factors influencing individual and / or collective DM processes.

2 BACKGROUND ON MATHS AND SOCIAL BASED DECISION MAKING SKILLS

2.1 Foundational background: rationality and uncertainty

The giant leap in mathematical approach to DM is arguably in 1202 with the publication of *Liber Abaci* by Fibonacci [5]. The next year hundreds saw great improvements to standardize Decision Methods aimed at calculate future events as an attempt to minimize risk. DM skills from mathematical viewpoint are originated in gambling: the player constantly estimates his/her chances of winning or losing. The field of decision analysis, originally mostly a mathematical discipline, has evolved into a useful method for industry and government. The core of the method is to help decision makers gain a greater understanding of the problems they face, both quantitatively and behaviourally. The expected utility theory, game theory and decision theory are important to understand how politicians and other stakeholders behave under condition of uncertainty and how decision models are constructed. But the limitation of the classical approach to probability in the context of decision theory is that the prediction of the outcome of a single event is based upon events that have already occurred, based on empirical evidence. However most decisions are disposed to the uncertainty of events that have not yet materialized. Expected value (or, where appropriate, utility) is the metric value of decision theory. The highest (or lowest if the assessment is cost related) expected value of a decision process is the best option in a portfolio of options, when all possible outcomes have been accounted for, with weights (probabilities) indicating the chance of occurrence (uncertainty).

People are not always rational and they do not always think about maximizing their own interests. Taleb [6] claims that the fundamentals of using probability distributions for estimating the impact of events on outcomes are idiosyncratic. This leads to what Taleb calls ludic fallacy for explaining the drawbacks of using the basic axioms of probability to estimate future uncertainty. Students are to understand the scope and limitations of mathematical decision-making methods and of computing tools.

2.2 Irrationality and VUCA contexts: reliability

There is no simple explanation for decision which seem sometimes irrational. There are limits to the cognitive and information-processing capacity we can devote to any judgement. Technical explanations cover inaccuracy in terms of project uncertainty, unreliable or out-dated data and the use of inappropriate forecasting models [7]. If sociological factors play a role, it is only a limited role. Both perspectives (economic and psychology) also focus on individual behaviour rather than social processes. However, sociological forces interact with psychological forces and will affect individual behaviour if groups act without any clear coordinating mechanism. In reality, on the interactions between individuals and groups in a social learning context, group forces and group motives are important, reflecting not only conformism, social imitation or conscious identification with group but also group-centred goals and behaviour.

The most fundamental capability of human beings is arguably conscious decision-making. Such decisions are made in non-emergency situations but often under a high degree of uncertainty (where uncertainty can be defined as the subject's conscious lack of knowledge about an object which is not yet clearly defined, in a context requiring action for decision). But in VUCA contexts, dynamicity and emergency are in the place. Mechanisms to detect early signs of crisis and react early enough are required. This point is a key element of High Reliable Organizations (HRO) [8] which seeks to understand the normal functioning of human-based decision systems by identifying the characteristics of HRO and explaining their exceptional performance. To reach a higher level of reliability, Roberts recommends flexibility in the decision-making process. Weick [1] identifies three characteristics of HRO in contexts where the error is unforgivable: information overload, constant turbulence, and increasing complexity. Unlike other theoretical frameworks on reliability (e.g. Theory of Normal Accidents), the HRO and Actionist currents have even the specificity to consider human behaviours as a source of reliability rather than failure. These organizations are able to create and maintain a state of collective watchfulness thanks to the quality of the interactions between their members [9]. Weick mentioned that respectful interactions, a system of roles, improvisation, and watchfulness are the four sources of reliability. A work on VUCA conditions from this theoretical works is supposed to answer the limits faced by maths-based decision making methods. The authors suggest to use this approaches which take into account VUCA parameters, as active learning courses.

3 LEARNING ACTIVITIES

3.1 Active learning activities

As course examples, In France, ESSEC Business School created the MOOC "*L'avenir de la decision : connaître et agir en complexité*" (Edgar Morin chair, <https://fr.coursera.org/learn/lavenir-de-la-decision>), composed of videos and lectures, including knowledge oriented courses. Aside, student may learn from real experiences, to develop and reinforce their decision competencies. In another context, in Spain, there are on-line university courses in decision engineering such as that given by the Rey Juan Carlos University of Madrid [10], to learn to make the best decisions with less time and to analyse them in a globalized world. With these courses, students are expected to improve the quality of decisions taken and, consequently, improve the results of decisions.

Various pedagogical models exist to foster collaborative dimensions and practical skills in formal STEM curricula (e.g. Problem-based learning, project-based learning).

In formal curriculum, the Disaster Week, initiated at Reykjavik University [11], exposes students to real-life engineering, as a multidisciplinary introductory course. With one week of team work, students are to develop an action plan for dealing with an unforeseen event of some complexity, demanding DM, fast based on incomplete information. Topic includes a natural disaster, e.g. a potentially devastating epidemic in Iceland or a volcanic eruption with the lava flow towards the city. This style of learning enforces the importance of teamwork, the need to gather information quickly, and one has to make decisions fast based on incomplete information. It permits to meet intended learning outcomes for freshmen around Maths-based DM.

At IMT Atlantique, French graduate engineering school, the Springfield serious game exposes students to real cases in order to show the complexity of actions and decisions in risky situation. The context is an accident which occurred in a nuclear plant. Each player has a specific role, with specific objectives and information (a plant manager, a safety engineer, and operators). Players have to work together in order to save the plants. In debriefings, students explain their behaviour and decisions.

3.2 Towards experiential learning activities

Future graduates are to be able to turn knowledge into skills, especially in DM. The complete development of a competence is better covered by various integrated learning activities, including real experiences or work-based learning models. For DM skills, in all its dimensions, experiential and cooperative learning is the key for Teaching & Learning innovation. Some courses permit to show by experience that DM is a complex process, particularly when the decision leads to irreversible consequences.

Still at IMT Atlantique, an inter-semester course (2 ECTS) trains students to take decisions and react in unexpected and unpredictable situations [12]. Using an experiential learning model as proposed in the French Naval Academy, the one week course has some outdoor elements in the sea environment for novices. The real experiential situations so selected reflect nautical risk scenarios with levels of complexity and time pressure (including Man Over Board exercises, cf. Figure 1), where specific decision skills are to be acquired or reinforced, such as risk and priority management, watchfulness, team management with respectful interactions, judgement and responsibility, etc. Participants also have to prepare a navigation (weather, equipment, refuelling, practical information), plan the stages, estimate the navigation times, the possible risks and dangers, prepare the most delicate passages, prepare fall-back solutions and identify success factors. Just like a project, the success of a sailing cruise requires a certain number of technical and human skills. In these real situations, flexibility constitutes the sources of reliability and performance. These in-context experiences are to be useful in an engineer career where responsibilities increase (e.g. decision-makers to face complexity, uncertainty and urgency). A first experience, as a non-expert from the environment, may create a learning-loop for future work-based situations including improvisation [1].

The experiential scenarios proposed rely on theoretical frameworks dealing with reliability. They use the four sources of reliability as assessment criteria and include situations with a high level of complexity, uncertainty, and time pressure that future decision makers are supposed to face in their future professional activities. As learning outcomes, the learning process should enable graduates:

- to tackle moral, ethical, and social issues of a situation;
- to identify sources of uncertainty, face complexity and continuously recognize and qualify the criticality of a situation, inc. its events and factors;

- to accept uncertainty, fix priorities and formulate judgment on situational events individually and collectively;
- to react flexibly to events and regularly assess the weight of an error in the DM process;
- to take initiative and responsibility on choices and actions during the situation, and reflect from experiences in order to increase resilience.

In [12], empirical evidence on motivational factors have been first analysed qualitatively. Based on direct observations and experiences, quantitative analysis is under investigation to determine how to better prepare future engineers to make more reliable decisions in VUCA environments. One's and team's DM skills are thus formalized in program components, as transversal, with aforementioned learning outcomes and VUCA-based progressive proficiency levels. Design-based research methodology is also under consideration in order to conceptualize experiential learning activities and iteratively analyse learner achievement and program coherency and framing.

Fig. 1. Collective urgent rescue.

Fig. 2. Job map, from [14].

4 CAREER BASED DECISION MAKING SKILLS

Investigations on courses including progressive VUCA circumstances should also facilitate the integration and career paths of young engineers in their professional life and workplace. Engineer diplomas greatly facilitate first job offers and open up on broad career possibilities in many economic fields where engineers may often exercise their potential as leaders and future decision makers. However, uncertainty and indecision often result from student appraisal of the career kaleidoscope. Some struggle to identify career directions and therefore need some time before feeling committed and being operational within their curriculum and first jobs. The European Lifelong Guidance Policy Network (<http://www.elgpn.eu/>) regards career management skills as competencies which help individuals to identify their existing skills, develop career learning goals and take action to enhance their careers.

It is thus critical to reinforce students' self-confidence, especially when considering that the recruitment market is becoming more and more demanding and competitive for newly graduated engineers. Students' perception of a profession can strongly influence their career choices. In addition, yet many students who have had only limited exposure to a profession may base their decisions on limited or distorted perspectives, for example a single internship or co-op experience, both positive and negative [13].

It is essential to provide students with means which will enable them to participate actively in their own learning and develop a long-term aspiration for future career paths. As learning outcomes, the learning process should enable graduates:

- to know oneself and analyse his/her set of skills;
- to gather information, identify options, and explore career options;
- to recognize and define one's choices;
- to define career paths, to plan and evaluate them, to select options;
- to gain flexibility and propose a coherent professional project inc. career orientation, and to combine personal development therewith.

Traditionally, educational institutions design career preparation programs which focus on making their students more attractive to potential employers. As example, in a University context, the Department of Guidance and Professional Insertion of the Foundation University-Enterprise of the Balearic Islands has realized the Occupational Guidance and Occupational Assistance Program. This non-compulsory program aims to guide and improve the possibilities of self-employment of the university graduates and students who are seeking employment. Concretely, it permits to improve employment opportunities by designing a personalized itinerary for job placement. This personalized itinerary consists in the realization of individualized sessions of professional orientation: how to properly take decisions to get a job, how to apply for a job interview to get an employment. Students learn the ability to make the right decisions from the individualized orientation sessions. At IMT Atlantique, a compulsory 63h career preparation course is in place since 2007, to disclose to students, via active workshops over three years, their career perspectives, enable them to participate actively in their own learning path, to build their future professional identity, and to plan proactively their future career [14], in VUCA workplace contexts.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In a rapidly changing world, the VUCA context requires now to rethink the vision for engineering education [15]. As seen today in the European society, the nature and dynamics of change creates unpredictability and future engineers are to manage complex situations with critical reasoning. Professional life environments are more than ever VUCA. This context makes decisions even more strategically critical. To prepare future engineers to make more reliable decisions in VUCA environments best benefit from experiential learning models, progressively all along a curricula, with a transversal skills approach. As Le Boterf defends it [16], a skill is only effective once it has been tested and validated thanks to its confrontation to reality. This system paper tends to thus support the coherent inclusion of active and engaging pedagogical models, with DM as a transversal skill, in association with three complementary and unified perspectives including learning outcomes:

- Maths-based DM, with rationality;
- Social-based DM, including people's interdependencies and social identities;
- Career-based DM, according to own career path.

A dedicated decision framework is to provide support for faculty staff to improve student competence in decision skills, interwoven with the learning of disciplinary knowledge and its application in professional environments. Mastering of these skills is to be assessed by various stages of complexity, e.g. partial application, realisation, adaptation to various VUCA situations, and anticipation. Societal responsibilities are

elements of DM and included in the three aforementioned perspectives. In fact, good decisions rely on many factors, context-dependant. The DM learning outcomes are to be indicated to provide a pragmatic guide to deal with the pressing ethical and social considerations. The aim is to ensure that students are educated, trained, and empowered to prioritize ethical and social considerations in their decisions, diminishing negative consequences in their future work, professional itinerary, and personal life.

The authors would like to acknowledge their colleagues from IMT Atlantique (French graduate Engineering School), Ecole Navale (French Naval Academy), Reykjavik University (Icelandic Engineering School), the Department of the Guidance and Professional Insertion at *Fundació Universitat-Empresa de les Illes Balears* (Spain), City of Glasgow College (VET School in Scotland), the Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework Partnership in Glasgow, and the *Fondation des Régions Européennes pour la Recherche, l'Éducation et la Formation*, who oriented the perspectives defended in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Weick K. E. (1993). The Collapse of Sensemaking in Organizations: The Mann Gulch Disaster. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 38(4), pp .628-652.
- [2] European Network for Accreditation of Engineering Education (2017), Glossary of Terminology. <https://tinyurl.com/ybs5yvvo>
- [3] ENAEE (2017). The EUR-ACE Framework Standards and Guidelines (EAFSG). The European Network for Accreditation of Engineering Education.
- [4] Crawley E. F., Malmqvist J., Lucas W. A., and Brodeur D. R. (2011). The CDIO Syllabus v2.0: An updated statement of goals for engineering education. In *Proc. of 7th International CDIO Conf., Copenhagen, Denmark*.
- [5] Fibonacci L. (2002). Fibonacci's Liber Abaci: A Translation into Modern English of Leonardo Pisano's *Book of Calculation*. trad. L. E. Sigler. Springer.
- [6] Taleb, N. (2007). *The Black Swan*. Random House, New York.
- [7] Vanston J.H. & Vanston L.K. (2004). Testing the Tea Leaves: Evaluating the Validity of Forecasts. *Research-Technology Management*, 47(5), pp. 33-39.
- [8] Rochlin G. (1996). Reliable Organizations: Present Research and Future Directions. *Journal of contingencies and crisis management*, Vo. 4, pp.55-60.
- [9] Vidal R., Arnaud C., and Tiberghien, B. (2010). *Fiabilité organisationnelle et maîtrise de la tension entre contrôle et écoute dans la gestion des feux de forêt : approche comparée France/Etats-Unis*. In French. *Télescope, numéro thématique sur la gestion des risques*, Vol. 16(2), pp. 59-74.
- [10] URJC (2017). *Máster Universitario en Ingeniería de Sistemas de Decisión*. In Spanish. Online course of Rey Juan Carlos University of Madrid, 60 credits. <https://online.urjc.es/>

- [11] Saemundsdottir I., Matthiasdottir A., Audunsson H., and Saevarsdottir G. A. (2012). Facing Disaster Learning by Doing at Reykjavik University. In *Proc. of the 8th Intl. CDIO Conference*, QUT, Brisbane, July 1-4.
- [12] Rouvrais, S. and Gaultier Le Bris, S. (2017). Breadth Experiential Courses to Flexibly Meet New Programme Outcomes for Engineers. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing Series*, Springer, Vol. 627(1).
- [13] Lichtenstein G., Loshbaugh H.G., Claar B., Chen H.L., Jackson K., and Sheppard D.S. (2009). An Engineering Major Does not (Necessarily) an Engineer Make: Career Decision Making among Undergraduate Engineering Majors. *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 98. Issue 3, pp. 227-234.
- [14] Rouvrais S. and Chelin N. (2010). Engineer Professional Identity: For an Early Clarification of Student's Perceptions. In *Proceedings of the 6th CDIO Conference*, École Polytechnique, Montréal.
- [15] Kamp A. (2016). Engineering Education in a Rapidly Changing World", 2nd edition, 4.TU Center for Engineering Education, Delft.
- [16] Le Boterf G. (2006). *Ingénierie et évaluation des compétences*. In French. Organisation Editions, 5th edition, 605 pages.